

Direct spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II) with nicotino hydroxamic acid in aqueous medium

Raghunathan Muthuselvi

Department of Chemistry, Sri. Meenakshi Government College for Women (Autonomous), Madurai-625 002, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : muthuselvi@mashankar@gmail.com

Manuscript received online 10 July 2012, revised 12 August 2012, accepted 13 August 2012

Abstract : A facile, sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of cobalt(II) in pure form, water, effluent and alloy sample using a newly synthesized reagent, nicotino hydroxamic acid (NHA). Cobalt(II) forms a pink coloured complex with NHA in borate buffer medium (pH 9.2). Under optimum conditions, the maximum absorption of the complex was measured at 610 nm. The Beer's law obeys in the range of 0.65 to 5.9 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ of cobalt(II). The molar absorptivity and the Sandell's sensitivity of the complex are $7.038 \times 10^4 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.0065 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ A}$, respectively. A detailed study of various interfering ions made the method more sensitive.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), nicotino hydroxamic acid (NHA), spectrophotometry, water, effluent and alloy sample.

Introduction

Metal ions in general and transition metals in particular are found to play an important role in industry, agriculture, plant nutrition, biological activities of living beings and medicine. Cobalt is an important essential micronutrient for all living systems. Cobalt is biologically more compatible with human systems. It is used in surgical implants and also for dental purposes, since it is not attacked by body liquids and does not irritate tissue¹. The importance of cobalt in animal nutrition has led to the development of procedures for determination in minute amounts in soils, plants and animal tissues. Cobalt is also mainly used in the manufacture of multipurpose steels, such as tool steels, high speed steels etc., and also in multivitamin tablets². Cobalt traces are technically important, which are used mainly as binder in the hard metal industry and as constituents of many alloys³. Cobalt toxicity causes different diseases including asthma, contact dermatitis, lung cancer and bronchitis⁴⁻⁷. Occupational exposure to hard metal dust, consisting of tungsten carbide (WC) and metallic cobalt particles is associated with increased lung cancer⁸. Although traces of cobalt is necessary for the synthesis of vitamin B-12, excessive administration of this trace element produces goiter and reduces thyroid activity⁹. A dietary intake of about 50 μg

cobalt, of which 40 μg in the form of vitamin B-12, maintains cobalt equilibrium in the human¹⁰. The determination of cobalt is valuable for the quality control of artificial and biological samples in a simple, selective, and sensitive manner.

Analytical chemistry :

Photocolorimetry, polarography and spectroscopy are among the most widely applied techniques for the accurate determination of metals at trace and ultratrace levels. Simplicity, quickness and accessibility are the basic advantages of the photocolorimetric methods. But often spectrophotometric methods suffer from limitations in sensitivity and selectivity, but are widely used due to the resulting experimental rapidity and simplicity. The selectivity and sensitivity of the spectrophotometric determination methods depend on the type of reaction and chromogenic reagent used (Sandell, 1959). Therefore, accurate determination of metals at trace and ultratrace levels using simple and rapid spectrophotometry is essential but it should also be highly selective and sensitive too. In continuation of the development of suitable methods for the determination of metals, especially in natural samples¹¹⁻¹⁵, this paper reports very sensitive and highly specific new spectrophotometric method for the trace de-

termination of cobalt using the reagent nicotino-hydroxamic acid (NHA).

Experimental

All chemicals/solvents used were of analytical reagent grade or the highest purity available. Doubly distilled de-ionized water, which is non-absorbent under ultraviolet radiation, was used throughout. Glass vessels were cleaned by soaking in acidified solutions of KMnO_4 or $\text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7$, followed by washing with concentrated HNO_3 and rinsed several times with de-ionized water.

Instruments :

An Elico digital pH meter was employed for pH measurements while absorbance measurements were carried out on SP-20 Spectronic spectrophotometer. All measurements were performed at room temperature.

Solutions and reagents :

The reagent nicotino-hydroxamic acid (NHA) was prepared by the reported procedure (Aliyu *et al.* 2008). Stock solution of ($2 \times 10^{-2} M$) NHA in ethanol has been used throughout the studies.

Stock solution of Co^{II} ($2.8 \times 10^{-4} M$) was prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in doubly distilled water containing a few drops of conc. HNO_3 in a 200 mL volumetric flask. The Co^{II} solution was standardized titrimetrically (Vogel, 1985). Working solutions were prepared by suitable dilutions with de-ionized water.

The solutions used for investigation of the effect of diverse ions were prepared from sulphate or nitrate of the tested cations and sodium or potassium salts of the tested anions.

The universal, acetate, borate and phosphate buffer solutions of varying pH values were prepared as described by Britton (1952).

Each filtered (with Whatman No. 42) environmental water sample (100 mL) evaporated nearly to dryness with 10 mL of concentrated HNO_3 in a fume cupboard and was heated with 10 mL of de-ionized water in order to dissolve the salts. The solution was then cooled and neutralized with dilute NH_4OH solution. The resulting solution was then filtered and quantitatively transferred into a 25 mL calibrated flask and made up to the mark with de-

ionized water. The effluent from the common tannery treatment plant of a tannery complex in Madurai was taken and diluted as per requirement.

Alloy material (0.1 g) was dissolved in concentrated HCl (15 mL) by warming. A little concentrated nitric acid (1 mL) was added and slowly evaporated to dryness. The residue was dissolved in 10 mL of 1 M HCl and the resulting solution was concentrated to *ca.* 5 mL, diluted to *ca.* 50 mL with distilled water, filtered and made up to 100 mL.

Recommended procedure :

A series of solutions containing up to 1.0 mL of buffer solution, 2 mL (0.02 M) of the reagent, 1 mL of sodium hydrogen carbonate (10%, w/v) and 1.0–10.0 mL ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) of metal solution was mixed with 2 mL of ethanol in a 25 mL measuring flask and then diluted up to the mark with distilled water. The resulting pink coloured solution was allowed to stand for a minute, the absorbance was measured at the maximum wavelength of 610 nm against a reagent blank prepared in the same manner. The calibration graphs were prepared by using the same procedure and were linear passing through the origin.

Results and discussion

Study of reaction between nicotino-hydroxamic acid (NHA) and Co^{II} ion :

Investigations were carried out to establish the most favorable conditions for the complexation reaction of nicotino-hydroxamic acid (NHA) with Co^{II} ion, to achieve the optimum conditions for maximum colour development in the determination of cobalt(II).

Electronic spectra and selection of the suitable wavelength :

The electronic absorption spectra of Co^{II} -NHA complex in the UV-Vis region exhibits maximum absorption at 610 nm. This peak has been used in all subsequent measurements of the absorbance. At this wavelength the absorption of both NHA and metal solution were negligible.

Effect of pH and buffer solution :

In order to determine the optimum pH value for complex formation, the reagent was allowed to react with the metal ion in borate buffer of pH 8.0–10.0, phosphate

buffer of pH 5.8–8.0 and universal buffer of pH 2.0–12.0. The most suitable pH value for the formation of the complex was determined by scanning the absorption spectra of the metal complex in solutions of different pH values using the same amount of the metal ion and the buffer as a blank within the wavelength range 200–800 nm. It was found that the borate buffer of pH 9.0–9.4 is the most suitable for developing Co^{II} complex.

Influence of time and sequence of addition :

The effect of time on complex formation was studied by measuring the absorbance of NHA-metal complex at different time intervals. The results show that the complex formed instantaneously and remained constant for more than 24 h. The obtained results for the effect of different sequences of addition (ligand-metal-buffer, metal-buffer-ligand and ligand-buffer-metal) to select the most suitable one for developing the colored complex showed that the sequence metal-ligand-buffer was the best one for the formation of Co^{II} complex with NHA.

Precision and accuracy :

The precision of the present method was evaluated by determining different concentrations of cobalt (each analyzed at least 6 times). The standard deviation ($n = 6$) was 0.07 for 1.96–5.22 μg of Co^{II} in 25 mL, indicating that this method is highly precise and reproducible.

Calibration graphs and statistical treatment of results :

Under the optimum reaction conditions for the spectrophotometric determination of NHA by chelation with Co^{II} ion, obedience to Beer's law was tested. On plotting the absorbance as a function of Co^{II} concentration, straight line was obtained in the range of 0.65 to 5.88 $\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$, in presence of borate buffer. The optimum ranges for the

Fig. 1. Validity of Beer's law.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on Co^{II}-NHA complex.

determination of Co^{II} were determined and the results are summarized with the other analytical parameters in Tables 1 and 2.

The apparent molar absorptivities were 7.038×10^4

Table 1. Determination of cobalt(II)							
Sl. no.	Co ^{II} taken ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	NHA method			Ammonium thiocyanate method ¹⁶		
		Co ^{II} found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery (%)	Error (%)	Co ^{II} found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Recovery (%)	Error (%)
1.	1.96	1.95	99.5	0.5	1.97	100.5	0.5
2.	2.61	2.62	100.4	0.4	2.60	99.6	0.4
3.	3.26	3.27	100.3	0.3	3.29	100.9	0.9
4.	3.92	3.90	99.5	0.5	3.89	99.2	0.8
5.	4.57	4.55	99.6	0.4	4.60	100.6	0.6
6.	5.22	5.20	99.6	0.4	5.25	100.5	0.5

Table 2. Statistical comparison

Sl. no.	Method	Av. error ^a (%)	S.D. ^a	C.V. ^a (%)
1.	Nicotinohydroxamic acid (NHA)	0.42	0.0688	0.164
2.	Ammonium thiocyanate	0.62	0.1772	0.286

^a6 replicates.

L mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ whereas the Sandell's sensitivity (Sandell, 1959) was 0.0065 µg cm⁻²/0.001 A. The high values of correlation coefficients and small values of standard deviations indicate the good linearity of all calibration graphs and the confirmatory of Beer's law to absorbance measurements.

Effect of foreign ions :

No interference was observed (relative error < 2.5% is considered no-interference) in the determination of NHA with Co^{II} from the presence of foreign ions in the present method. The results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Interference studies

Amount of cobalt(II) taken = 5.22 µg mL⁻¹

Foreign ions	Tolerance limit (µg mL ⁻¹)
Carbonate, molybdate, citrate, phosphate	70
Bicarbonate, iodide, bismuth(II) and iron(III) ^a , sulphate, bromide	60
Acetate, chloride, cadmium(II) and barium(II)	52
Hydroxide, thiosulphate, oxalate, borate, fluoride, magnesium(II), sodium(I), zirconium(II), tin(II), zinc(II), strontium(III) and lead(II)	40
Nitrate, manganese(II) ^b and calcium(II)	25
Chromium(III) ^c , nickel(II) ^c , ammonium(I), aluminium(III) and lithium(I)	20

^aMasked with NaF (1% w/v, 5 mL), ^bMasked with KI (1% w/v, 5 mL), ^cMasked with sodium tartarate (1% w/v, 5 mL).

Applications :

The present method was successfully applied to the determination of cobalt in environmental, industrial effluent and alloy sample. In view of the unknown composition of environmental water sample, the same equivalent portion of the sample was analyzed for cobalt content; the recovery in the "spiked" (added to the samples

before the mineralization or dissolution) sample is in good agreement.

Determination of cobalt in environmental water and industrial effluent samples :

An aliquot (1–6 mL) of this solution was pipetted into a 25 mL calibrated flask, and the cobalt content was determined as described under recommended procedure. The analysis of environmental water sample and effluent sample collected from a tannery for cobalt(II) was performed and the results are given in Tables 4 and 5. A close examination of the table reveals that the presently developed method can be applied for determination of cobalt in these samples with a high degree of accuracy and precision.

Table 4. Determination of cobalt(II) in natural water sample

Sl. no.	Co ^{II} added (µg mL ⁻¹)	Co ^{II} found (µg mL ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
1.	1.96	1.95	99.5
2.	2.61	2.63	100.8
3.	3.26	3.25	99.7
4.	3.92	3.90	99.5
5.	4.57	4.58	100.2
6.	5.22	5.20	99.6

Table 5. Determination of cobalt(II) in effluent (tannery) sample

Sl. no.	Co ^{II} added (µg mL ⁻¹)	Co ^{II} found (µg mL ⁻¹)	Recovery (%)
1.	1.96	1.94	99.0
2.	2.61	2.58	98.8
3.	3.26	3.24	99.4
4.	3.92	3.88	99.0
5.	4.57	4.55	99.6
6.	5.22	5.18	99.2

Determination of cobalt in alloy sample :

Suitable aliquots of the sample high speed steel (3082) was analyzed for the determination of cobalt(II) in alloy sample by following the recommended procedure. The absorbance values were referred to the pre-determined calibration plot to compute the amount of cobalt present and the results are given in Table 6. The results show that the recoveries are in good agreement with the certified values, indicating that the proposed method can be used in routine analysis of the metal in the alloy.

Table 6. Alloy analysis : Determination of cobalt(II) in high speed steel

Sample composition (Co %)	Certified value ^a	Sl. no.	Amount of alloy taken ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Amount of Co ^{II} found ($\mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$)	Amount of Co ^{II} found (%)	Av. Co ^{II} found (%)
High speed steel (ITA LABS 3082), (W-17, Cr-4.0 ^b , V-0.9, Si-0.32, Mo-0.30, Mn-0.30 ^c , C-0.75, Rest-Fe ^d)	4.82	1.	20.00	1.44	4.79	
		2.	30.00	1.90	4.75	
		3.	40.00	2.39	4.80	4.78
		4.	50.00	2.89	4.81	
		5.	60.00	3.33	4.76	

^aCertified by the manufacturers, ^bmasked with sodium tartarate (1% w/v, 3 mL), ^cmasked with KI (1% w/v, 5 mL), ^dmasked with NaF (1% w/v, 5 mL).

Conclusions :

The present research work has demonstrated the feasibility of the use of UV-Vis spectroscopy and complexation reaction for determination of cobalt(II). The determination process is based on the ability of cobalt(II) to form stable 1 : 1 (M : L) complexes with nicotino hydroxamic acid (NHA). The method is simple and rapid with greater sensitivity, better selectivity, and improved precision and avoids the precious steps of solvent extraction, and reduces the cost and toxicity while enhancing the sensitivity, selectivity, and molar absorptivity. The proposed method is applied for determination of cobalt(II) in trace amounts with high precision and good accuracy. The proposed method using NHA in aqueous medium is not only one of the most sensitive method for the determination of cobalt but also is excellent in terms of selectivity and simplicity. Therefore, this method will be successfully applied to the monitoring of trace amounts of cobalt in real, environmental, industrial effluent and alloy sample.

Acknowledgement

The author would like to express her appreciation for the financial support extended by University Grants Commission (SERO), Hyderabad, for doing this valuable research work. The author also expresses her heartfelt gratitude to the Principal, Head and Colleagues, of the Department of Chemistry, Sri. Meenakshi Government College for Women (Autonomous), Madurai, Tamilnadu, for their valuable guidance and moral support to finish this work.

References

1. Dietary Supplement Fact Sheet : Vitamin B₁₂, <http://ods.od.nih.gov/>
2. N. N. Greenwood and H. Earnshaw, "Chemistry of the Elements", 1st ed., 1989, 1321.
3. A. A. Jensen and F. Tuchsén, *Crit. Rev. Toxicol.*, 1990, **20**, 427.
4. M. De Boeck, S. Lardau, J. P. Buchet, M. K. Volders and D. Lison, *Environ. Mol. Mutagen.*, 2000, **36**, 151.
5. M. De Boeck, K. Volders and D. Lison, *Mutat. Res.*, 2004, **548**, 127.
6. V. Verougstraete, A. Mallants, J. P. Buchet, B. Swennen and D. Lison, *Am. J. Res. and Crit. Care Med.*, 2004, **170**, 162.
7. D. Lison, M. De Boeck, V. Verougstraete and M. K. Volders, *Occup. Environ. Med.*, 2001, **58**, 619.
8. M. De Boeck, N. Lombaert, S. De Backer, R. Finsy, D. Lison and M. K. Volders, *Mutagenesis*, 2003, **18**, 177.
9. D. G. Barceloux, *J. Toxicol. Clin. Toxicol.*, 1999, **37**, 201.
10. B. Venugopal and T. D. Luckiy, "Metal Toxicity in Mamals", 2nd ed., Plenum Press, New York, 1999, p. 284.
11. K. Girish Kumar and R. Muthuselvi, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 2001, **137**, 25.
12. K. Girish Kumar and R. Muthuselvi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2001, **13**, 337.
13. K. Girish Kumar and R. Muthuselvi, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2006, **61**, 28.
14. K. Girish Kumar and R. Muthuselvi, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2011, **23**, 3620.
15. R. Muthuselvi and K. Vigneswari, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2011, **24**, 1579.
16. *Encyclopedia of Industrial Chemical Analysis*, 1970, **10**, 366.

